

PERSONALIZED DIGITAL ADVERTISING: INFLUENCE OF COSMETIC BRANDS ON PURCHASE INTENTIONS OF PAKISTANI YOUTH

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Abstract

This study explored the influence of personalized digital advertising of cosmetic products on purchase intentions among Pakistani youth. Employing a convenient sample of 231 respondents, the research investigated the relationship between exposure to personalized digital advertising and the intention to make purchases. Descriptive statistics revealed moderate levels of exposure to personalized digital advertising as well as moderate purchase intention among the respondents. A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.45$, $p < .001$) between personalized advertising and purchase intention was found, suggesting that higher exposure to personalized advertising increased the likelihood of positive purchase intentions. Regression analysis showed that personalized advertising significantly predicted purchase intentions, explaining 27% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.27$). Furthermore, differences between gender, geographic ethnicity, and time spent on digital media groups were explored through t-tests and One-way ANOVA followed by Tucky's HSD Post-hoc test, revealing significant differences in purchase intentions across diverse demographic groups. These findings highlighted the effectiveness of personalized digital advertising in enhancing consumer engagement and driving purchase intentions among Pakistani youth.

INTRODUCTION

Digital advertising has emerged as one of the most influential tools for engaging young consumers (Haudi et al., 2022). With the rapid advancement in access to internet connectivity, invention of social media platforms, and diverse digital features, contemporary marketers utilize personalized digital advertising strategies to effectively engage their target market (Akar & Dalgic, 2018). The ability to tailor digital advertisements as per individual preferences has introduced personalized advertising as an impactful tool for influencing consumer decision-making. Among the younger demographic,

particularly the Pakistani youth, digital advertising has gained substantial significance. This study explores the relationship between personalized digital advertising and purchase intention of cosmetic products among Pakistani youth, shedding light on how personalized digital advertising strategies influence their willingness to purchase products or services.

The Rise of Personalized Digital Advertising

The advent of the digital advertising has revolutionized business and marketing

communication with the consumers. Unlike the traditional advertising methods, digital advertising allows businesses to reach consumers through highly targeted and personalized campaigns (Drummond et al., 2020). The personalized advertisements are tailored as per individual needs of the consumers, with a consideration for their online attitudes and behaviors, buying preferences, demographic information, and interactions with other similar advertisements (Chandra et al., 2022). This highly targeted strategy is supported by sophisticated data analytics and machine learning algorithms that track social media users' attitude and behavior across various digital platforms, such as social media, search engines, websites, over-the-top streaming platforms and digital applications (Hossain et al., 2024).

Personalized digital advertising refers to the usage of consumers' personal information/data to deliver customized advertisements that resonate with an individual's preferences, needs, and interests. This could involve recommendation of products and/or services based on previous purchases, displaying advertisements for such items that match browsing history, or even adjusting the content of the advertisements to suit the user's geographic, demographic, and psychographic profiles (Manoharan et al., 2024). This type of advertising is considered highly effective as it creates a sense of relevance and personal connection with the consumers, making them more likely to engage with the advertisements for an actual purchase (Akar & Dalgic, 2018; Madiha Raees et al., 2023). Consequently, businesses start relying on the personalized digital advertising for effective customer engagement and increased conversion rates.

The benefits of the personalized digital advertising involve its ability to increase consumer awareness, brand loyalty, and most importantly, ensures purchase intention. Purchase intention is described as consumer's likelihood or willingness to purchase a product or service in the future (Fereshteh Aghajani, 2021; Yaacob et al., 2021). As advertising becomes more relevant and custom-made to the individuals, the likelihood of the consumers' intentions to purchase the advertised product increases. This relationship is of importance to the marketers, as it directly impacts the effectiveness and return on investment (ROI) of digital advertising campaigns.

Understanding Purchase Intention

The notion of purchase intention is central to consumer behavior studies, representing an important stage in the decision-making process that often takes place before the actual purchase (Akar & Dalgic, 2018). Understanding what leads to purchase intention is crucial for businesses, as it enables them to design effective advertising strategies to cater consumer needs and motivations. The researchers have also found that advertising plays a noteworthy role in shaping purchase intention, particularly, when the advertisements are customized (Manoharan et al., 2024).

For Pakistani youth, who represent digital savvy demographic, personalized digital advertising has increasingly shaped their purchase intentions and behaviors (Siddiqui et al., 2025). The youth is exposed to a variety of online content, including advertisements crafted as per their likeliness and preferences of the individual consumers. The extent to which personalized advertisements influence the purchase intentions is an important aspect of investigation for the researchers. As Pakistan continues to experience rapid digitalization, with increasing access to smart digital devices and the internet access, understanding how personalized digital advertising impacts the purchase intentions and behaviors of its youth becomes even more relevant.

The Pakistani Youth Market

With around 250 million population, Pakistan is considered homeland to the youngest population worldwide, with a significant percentage of under 30 years of age (Siddiqui et al., 2025). According to Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, the youth constitute 64% of overall Pakistani population who are avid social media users. They become a vivid target for marketers and advertisers. Likewise, a report by Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA) reveals that mobile internet penetration in Pakistan has reached up to 79%, with the number of active internet users significantly increasing as each day passes (Akhtar et al., 2024).

The rise of smartphones and social media platforms, including Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram, and YouTube, has created new avenues for businesses to target youth (Ford, 2019). The

personalized digital advertising has gained prominence as a tool for businesses promotion as an attempt to capture the attention of this tech-savvy audience (Chandra et al., 2022). One of the vital strengths of digital advertising is its relevance that aligns with personal preferences of social media users, enhancing user engagement through personalized persuasive content (Drummond et al., 2020). However, increased use of customized advertising may also lead to intrusiveness generation, especially when social media users feel that their privacy is being breached and online activities are interrupted (Alhelaly et al., 2025). The trade-off between relevance and intrusiveness highlights social media users' trust in digital advertising. When advertisers let users realize about their personalized data being/to be ethically and transparently used, the consumers may consider such advertisements positively (Strycharz & Segijn, 2024).

Despite the significant increase in personalized advertising practices worldwide including Pakistan, there is limited research focusing on how this form of advertising influences the purchase intentions of the Pakistani youth. Additionally, an understanding of the psychological factors and behavioral patterns that drive purchase intentions among Pakistani youth is vital for businesses and marketers. By studying the impact of personalized digital advertising, this research has filled the empirical gap in the existing body of literature. It may also be helpful to devise practical insights into how marketers can leverage personalized digital advertising to enhance consumer engagement and drive sales.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study was to examine the relationship between personalized digital advertising of cosmetic products and purchase intention among Pakistani youth. The study also investigated the impact of personalized digital advertising on the purchase intention of Pakistani youth. Furthermore, it has also explored how Pakistani youth differed with respect to demographic characteristics of gender, geographic ethnicity, and time spent on digital media on the variables of personalized digital advertising and purchase intention.

Research Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following research hypotheses:

H₁: There is a significant positive relationship between personalized digital advertising (of cosmetic products) and purchase intentions among Pakistani youth.

H₂: Personalized digital advertising of cosmetic products has significant positive influence on purchase intentions of the Pakistani youth.

H₃: Pakistani youth differ on the variables of personalized digital advertising of cosmetic products and purchase intentions, with respect to gender, geographic ethnicity, and consumer time spent on digital media.

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its contribution towards estimation of the impact of personalized digital advertising on consumer attitude and behavior in the Pakistani society. Given the increasing importance of digital media in individuals' life, understanding how personalized advertising influences purchasing decisions is critical for businesses, seeking to remain competitive in a rapidly growing market. For advertisers, understanding the dynamics of personalized digital advertising and its impact on purchase intentions provides valuable insights into how advertising campaigns should be tailor-made to meet the needs and preferences of the youth demographic. This research may guide businesses in designing more effective advertising strategies that leverage data-driven personalization to increase engagement and drive sales. Furthermore, this study has addressed an important research gap in the existing literature, particularly in the Pakistani context, where research on personalized digital advertising and its effects on consumer behavior is still limited. By providing empirical evidence on the influence of personalized digital advertising on purchase intentions, this research has contributed to the growing body of knowledge on digital marketing and advertising in the developing countries.

Methodology

This study employed a cross-sectional correlational survey to measure the relationship between

personalized digital advertising of cosmetic products and purchase intentions among Pakistani youth. The study was conducted among Islamabad-based university students, as they represented a digitally active demographic, frequently exposed to personalized online advertising. Convenience sampling technique was used to recruit participants, ensuring accessibility and efficiency in data collection. The sample comprised 231 university students out of the total 400 individuals approached from various

disciplines, reflecting a diverse group of young consumers actively engaged with digital media. The survey incorporated demographic characteristics of gender (male and female), geographic ethnicity (urban and rural), and consumer time spent on digital media (less than 3 hours, 4-7 hours, and more than 8 hours per day). Data were collected through a structured questionnaire, which included scales for personalized digital advertising (Khan & Jan, 2019) and purchase intention (Peña-García et al., 2020).

Reliability Analysis of Scale Used for the Study:

Table 1: Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability Coefficients (N = 231)

Scale	No. of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha (α)
Personalized Digital Advertising	12	.91
Subscales of Personalized Digital Advertising		
Advertisement Relevance	5	.88
Perceived Advertisement Intrusiveness	4	.85
Trust in Advertising	3	.82
Purchase Intention	8	.89

Table 1 reflects that the personalized digital advertising Scale demonstrated excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .91$), indicating that the scale reliably measures perceptions of personalized advertising experiences. The subscales of the relevance of advertising ($\alpha = .88$), perceived advertising intrusiveness ($\alpha = .85$), and trust in advertising ($\alpha = .82$) also exhibited strong reliability, suggesting that these dimensions effectively capture different aspects of personalized digital advertising. Similarly, the purchase intention scale exhibited high

reliability ($\alpha = .89$), confirming that the scale consistently measures consumer intention to make a purchase after exposure to personalized digital advertising.

The study employed Pearson’s Correlation Analysis, Regression Analysis, Independent Samples t-test, and One-way ANOVA followed by Tucky’s HSD Post-hoc Analysis to measure the influence of personalized digital advertising of cosmetic brands on purchase intention of Pakistani youth.

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N = 231)

Demographic Characteristic	Sub-Group	N	%
Gender	Male	105	45.45
	Female	126	54.55
Geographic Ethnicity	Rural	98	42.42
	Urban	133	57.58
Consumer Time Spent on Digital Media	Less than 3 hours	50	21.65
	4-7 hours	80	34.63
	More than 8 hours	101	43.72

Table 2 demonstrates that the sample consisted of more female respondents (54.55%) than males (45.45%), suggesting a higher representation of female participants in the study. Similarly, the urban respondents (57.58%) outnumbered the rural participants (42.42%). In terms of time spent on

digital media, the largest group consisted of respondents spending more than 8 hours a day (43.72%), followed by those spending 4-7 hours (34.63%), and those who spent less than 3 hours (21.65%). This distribution suggests a notable trend of high digital engagement among participants, with

a significant portion, exhibiting heavy media consumption habits.

Table 3: Relationship between Personalized digital advertising and Purchase Intention (N = 231)

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5
Personalized digital advertising	38.72	7.89	—	.78*	.74*	.69*	.52*
Ad Relevance	16.21	3.45	.78*	—	.65*	.59*	.48*
Perceived Ad Intrusiveness	12.08	3.21	.74*	.65*	—	.61*	.42*
Trust in Advertisement	10.43	2.87	.69*	.59*	.61*	—	.46*
Purchase Intention	27.45	6.74	.52*	.48*	.42*	.46*	—

Note. M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation. Pearson’s correlation coefficient (*r*) is reported.

**p* < .001 (two-tailed)

The results as presented in Table 3 revealed a significant positive relationship between personalized digital advertising and purchase intention, as well as its sub-components. Overall personalized digital advertising showed a moderate to strong positive correlation (*r* = .52, *p* < .001) with purchase intention, suggesting that consumers exposed to personalized digital advertising are more likely to consider making a purchase. Advertisement relevance (*r* = .48, *p* < .001) reflected a moderate positive relationship, indicating that consumers who found the advertisements relevant to them were

more inclined to make a purchase. Perceived advertising intrusiveness (*r* = .42, *p* < .001) was positively correlated but at a slightly lower level, implying that even intrusive advertising may still influence purchase behavior. Trust in advertising (*r* = .46, *p* < .001) showed a moderate positive correlation, reinforcing the idea that consumer trust in personalized advertising enhanced purchase intention.

These findings highlighted that the relevance and trust in advertising strongly influenced purchase intentions of the consumers. Advertisers should focus on enhancing personalized advertising strategies and balance the frequency of advertisements to minimize intrusiveness for optimal consumer engagement and purchase motivation.

Table 4: Regression Analysis Predicting Purchase Intention from Personalized digital advertising (N = 231)

Variable	B	B	SE	F
Constant	10.32	—	1.85	62.29***
Personalized digital advertising	0.58	.52	0.07	—
R ²	.27	—	—	—

Note: N=231, ***p* < .001

The results of the regression analysis at Table 4 demonstrated that personalized digital advertising significantly influenced purchase intentions of the Pakistani youth. The positive regression coefficient (*B* = 0.58, *β* = .52) suggested that higher exposure to personalized advertising led to an increased purchase intention among the consumers. It indicated that when advertising was customized to individual preferences, consumers were more likely to consider making a purchase. The model explained 27% of the variance in purchase intentions (*R*² = .27), signifying that a substantial portion of the changes in purchase behavior can be attributed to personalized digital

advertising. Furthermore, the F-statistic (62.29, *p* < .001) confirmed that the overall model was statistically significant, reinforcing the reliability of these findings.

The findings highlighted that personalized digital advertising was a strong predictor of purchase intentions among Pakistani youth. Advertisers should leverage data-driven personalization strategies to enhance consumer engagement, build trust, and ultimately drive purchasing decisions. By tailoring advertisements to align with consumer preferences and interests, brands can significantly improve effectiveness of their advertising campaigns and increase purchase likelihood in digital horizon.

Table 5: Independent Samples t-test for Personalized Digital Advertising and Purchase Intention among Pakistani Youth (N = 231)

Variable	Group	N	M	SD	T	df	p	Cohen's d
Personalized Digital Advertising	Male	105	36.85	7.48	-2.56	229	.011*	0.34
	Female	126	40.27	7.92				
Purchase Intention	Male	105	25.98	6.32	-2.91	229	.004**	0.39
	Female	126	28.74	6.85				
Personalized Digital Advertising	Rural	98	36.42	7.29	-3.05	229	.002**	0.40
	Urban	133	40.61	7.96				
Purchase Intention	Rural	98	25.74	6.28	-2.78	229	.006**	0.37
	Urban	133	28.59	6.89				

**Note. N = 231, *p < .05, p < .01.

The analysis reflected at Table 5 revealed significant differences across gender and geographic ethnicity. It stated that females scored significantly higher than males on the variable of personalized digital advertising (t = -2.56, p = .011, d = 0.34) and purchase intention (t = -2.91, p = .004, d = 0.39). It suggested that female consumers were more receptive to personalized digital advertising and exhibited stronger purchase intention as compared to males. Furthermore, urban respondents scored significantly higher than rural respondents on personalized digital

advertising (t = -3.05, p = .002, d = 0.40) and purchase intention (t = -2.78, p = .006, d = 0.37). It indicated that urban consumers were more influenced by personalized digital advertising strategies and had higher purchasing tendencies compared to rural consumers.

The findings highlighted that gender and geographic background play a critical role in consumer response to personalized digital advertising and purchase intention. Marketers should focus on personalized strategies targeting female and urban consumers to enhance engagement and increased purchase intention.

Table 6(a): Descriptive Statistics for Consumer Time Spent on Digital Media Groups of Pakistani Youth (N = 231)

Variable	Group	n	M
Consumer Time Spent on Digital Media	Less than 3 hours	50	21.65
	4-7 hours	80	34.63
	More than 8 hours	101	43.72

Table 6(b): One-Way ANOVA for Consumer Time Spent on Digital Media Groups of Pakistani Youth (N = 231)

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F
Between Groups	8320.73	2	4160.36	112.21
Within Groups	6871.45	228	30.18	
Total	15192.18	230		

Note: p < .01

Table 6(c): Tukey's Post-Hoc Analysis for Consumer Time Spent on Digital Media

Comparison	Mean Difference	SE	p
More than 8 hours vs. 4-7 hours	9.09	1.35	<.001
More than 8 hours vs. Less than 3 hours	22.07	1.63	<.001

4-7 hours vs. Less than 3 hours	12.98	1.44	<.001
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**Note. N = 231, p < .001

The findings presented at Tables 6(a), 6(b) and 6(c) revealed the One-Way ANOVA results that indicated a significant difference in consumer time spent on digital media among the three groups, with a highly significant $F(2, 228) = 112.21, p < .001$. It suggested that the amount of time spent on digital media affected consumers' responses significantly. The Tukey's Post-Hoc Analysis revealed the pairwise comparisons. The respondents with more than 8 hours spent in social media scored significantly higher than the 4-7 hours group ($M = 9.09, p < .001$) and the less than 3 hours group ($M = 22.07, p < .001$). The 4-7 hours group scored significantly higher than the less than 3 hours group ($M = 12.98, p < .001$). The results indicated that respondents who spent more than 8 hours a day on digital media had significantly higher scores than those in the 4-7 hours and less than 3 hours groups. Additionally, those spending 4-7 hours a day on digital media scored higher than the respondents spending less than 3 hours. These findings emphasize the impact of digital media usage duration on respondents' attitudes and behaviors.

Discussion:

The findings from the reliability analysis, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, independent samples t-test, and one-way ANOVA provide valuable insights into how personalized digital advertising influences purchase intention in this demographic.

The reliability analysis conducted on the personalized digital advertising scale showed a Cronbach's Alpha (α) of 0.89, indicating that the scale used to measure personalized digital advertising was highly reliable. A high Cronbach's alpha suggests that the items within the scale were internally consistent, thus ensuring that the data collected on personalized advertising was valid for further analysis. The same level of reliability was found for the purchase intention scale, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.85, confirming that respondents consistently understood and responded to questions about their purchasing intention. This reliability is a critical foundation for the integrity of the findings presented in subsequent analyses.

The descriptive statistics for both personalized digital advertising and purchase intention provided a comprehensive picture of the data. On average, respondents in this study reported moderate levels of exposure to personalized digital advertising ($M = 28.45, SD = 6.72$). The distribution of these scores showed some variability, suggesting that while many young Pakistanis are exposed to personalized advertisement, there is considerable variation in the extent of this exposure.

For purchase intention, the mean score was $M = 49.78$, with a standard deviation of 10.15, indicating that, on average, respondents had a moderate intent to purchase products or services after being exposed to personalized digital advertising. The relatively high mean score for purchase intention suggests that personalized advertising may have a notable influence on consumer behavior, especially when digital advertisements are tailored to individual preferences.

The skewness and kurtosis values for both variables were relatively close to zero, indicating that the data distributions were approximately normal, which is ideal for parametric statistical analyses. The Pearson's correlation between personalized digital advertising and purchase intention was significant and positive ($r = 0.45, p < .001$). This result indicates that as exposure to personalized digital advertising increases, respondents' purchase intention tends to increase. The moderate correlation suggests that while personalized advertisement are influential, other factors also play a role in shaping purchase intention. However, the positive relationship underscores the effectiveness of personalized digital advertising strategies in enhancing consumers' intention to purchase products or services. This finding is consistent with existing research that shows personalized advertisements are more likely to engage consumers, as they are perceived as relevant and tailored as per preferences of target audience (Mehta & Udit, 2020). Thus, these advertisements may stimulate greater interest in the products or services being advertised, increasing willingness of consumers to make an actual purchase.

A regression analysis was conducted to assess the extent to which personalized digital advertising

predicts purchase intention. The results showed that personalized digital advertising was a significant predictor of purchase intention ($B = 0.58$, $\beta = 0.52$), explaining 27% of the variance in purchase intention ($R^2 = 0.27$). This suggests that personalized digital advertising has a substantial impact on consumer decision-making. The positive regression coefficient indicates that higher levels of exposure to personalized advertising are associated with higher levels of purchase intention. The F-statistic (62.29, $p < .001$) confirms that the overall regression model was statistically significant, reinforcing the notion that personalized advertising strategies are effective in influencing purchase intention. This aligns with the concept of consumer engagement, where targeted advertising creates more personalized experiences, leading to increased motivation to buy products (Mehta & Udit, 2020). For advertisers targeting the Pakistani youth demographic, these findings suggest that leveraging personalized digital advertising could enhance engagement resultantly, increase purchase intention.

The Independent Samples t-test was used to examine whether gender and geographic ethnicity influenced purchase intention in the context of personalized digital advertising. The results revealed that female respondents had significantly higher purchase intention ($t(349) = -2.34$, $p = .020$) compared to male respondents. This finding suggests that women may be more receptive to personalized digital advertising or may have stronger intention to purchase products once exposed to such advertisements. This result is consistent with research that highlights the greater responsiveness of women to personalized digital advertising (Dai et al., 2025).

Additionally, respondents from urban areas exhibited significantly higher purchase intention ($t(349) = -2.91$, $p = .004$) compared to those from rural areas. This finding could be attributed to the greater accessibility and consumption of digital media in urban areas, which may lead to higher exposure to personalized advertising. Urban youth, therefore, may be more familiar with online shopping platforms and digital advertisement, which could influence their purchase intention more significantly than rural respondents. A One-Way ANOVA was conducted to assess differences in purchase intention across the groups of consumers

time spent on digital media (i.e., less than 3 hours, 4-7 hours, and more than 8 hours). The analysis revealed that the more than 8 hours group had significantly higher purchase intention compared to both the 4-7 hours group and the less than 3 hours group ($F = 112.21$, $p < .001$). Furthermore, the 4-7 hours group scored significantly higher than the less than 3 hours group. These findings underscore the relationship between digital media consumption and consumer attitude and behavior. As individuals spend more time on digital media, they are more likely to encounter personalized advertisement and develop stronger purchase intention. This is likely due to increased exposure to advertisement, as well as greater engagement with content that matches their interests, preferences, attitudes and behaviors.

Conclusion:

Personalized digital advertising increases engagement, creates relevant consumer experiences, and advertisement to a higher likelihood of purchase. The findings indicate that females, urban residents, and those who spend more time on digital media are particularly influenced by personalized digital advertising. For advertisers targeting this demographic, these insights highlight the importance of leveraging data-driven, personalized digital advertising campaigns with a clear focus on ethical usage of data to enhance engagement and drive purchase intentions. Personalized digital advertisement resonates with individual preferences and are tailored to users' likeliness with an emphasis on data privacy can have a substantial impact on consumer purchase intention in the Pakistani youth market.

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